

WORLD PROGRESS TOWARD FUSION ENERGY

N. Anne Davies

Office of Fusion Energy
Office of Energy ResearchINTRODUCTION

There has been significant progress in fusion research during the last three years. Much of the technical progress has been achieved through international collaboration in magnetic fusion research. This progress has stimulated political interest in a multinational effort, aimed at designing and, possibly constructing the world's first experimental fusion reactor. This interest was reflected in several recent summit-level discussions involving President Mitterand, General Secretary Gorbachev, and President Reagan. Most recently, the European Community (EC), Japan, the United States, and the U.S.S.R. have decided to begin serious preparation for taking the next step toward practical fusion energy. These parties have agreed to begin the design and supporting R&D for an International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) under the auspices of the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). The initiation of an international program to prepare for a fusion test reactor does not imply that all of the technical problems of fusion have been solved. It does indicate that fusion research has begun a significant transition with respect to the central goal of the program. Fusion research was initiated about 35 years ago. The ultimate objective of the program was to create an inexhaustible, safe and environmentally sound energy source. However, the fundamental goal was to establish the scientific feasibility of fusion. It soon became apparent that neither the science nor the technology of the time were adequate to reach even this basic goal.

The progress of the past decade has changed this situation completely. The science and technology, which have been developed, now appear to be adequate to the task. Scientific feasibility is a concept that is difficult to define precisely. However, many fusion scientists have become convinced that it is no longer in question.¹ Consequently, the focus of interest in fusion research has begun to shift to the questions of engineering feasibility.

The scientific evidence that supports the belief in the scientific feasibility of fusion is extensive. However, at least part of the confidence rests on the fact that two completely different approaches have succeeded in producing fusion reaction conditions in the laboratory; magnetic confinement in the tokamak, and laser driven inertial confinement. Magnetic fusion experiments, for example, have produced plasma conditions sufficient to release 10 MW of fusion power at an energy gain of 30 percent. From these experiments, both approaches have clearly identified the scientific problems that remain to be solved and, more important, have identified sound experimental programs to find their solution. These results have enabled the U.S. to design experiments that could investigate the physics of an ignited plasma--the final scientific goal of magnetic confinement fusion--by 1997. Whatever the definition of scientific feasibility, the experimental results indicate that it is possible to release fusion energy in the laboratory. The central question for fusion R&D to address over the next decade is whether these results can lead to a practical fusion energy application. The next goal for fusion research is to demonstrate engineering feasibility.

It appears that the basic physics of both the magnetic and inertial confinement approaches will result in fusion energy being released in large amounts. This does not pose a major problem for fusion reactors, which studies^{2&3} show should be in the 500 to 1000 MWe range. However, it does pose a problem for fusion development. The experimental facilities required to finish the development of a practical fusion energy source will be on the same scale as reactors and produce about 1000 MW, if operated with a duty cycle adequate for their purpose.

Historically, the scale of the facilities required to produce fusion conditions has been an important factor in determining the pace of fusion development. This is true for at least three reasons. First, larger scale facilities take longer to construct. Second, large-scale fusion facilities require a great deal of preparatory technology and engineering development. Third, as the cost of the developmental facilities rises, the burden of justifying their cost in terms of the ultimate benefit of the development also increases. Considering the rapid progress of fusion science and technology, the future pace of fusion energy development will most likely be determined by how rapidly the next stage facilities can be justified. It is in this context that international collaboration could play a critical role in timely development of fusion. International collaboration can spread the risks and costs of the next stage of fusion development and thereby increase the probability of timely decisions on new facilities. If fusion energy has a role to play in the future, it will be in contributing to the development of an environmentally acceptable global energy supply. It is entirely fitting that it be developed through an international collaborative effort.

This paper will summarize the rapid progress that has been made in fusion science and technology, as well as what remains to be done. It will also emphasize the progress that has been made in building the unprecedented level of international collaboration that is so important for ensuring rapid progress in the future.

THE STATUS OF INTERNATIONAL FUSION DEVELOPMENT

Magnetic confinement fusion research is carried out mainly by the European Community, Japan, the U.S. and the U.S.S.R. There are also smaller programs in Canada and China, as well as modest fusion-related research in 25 developing countries. The world effort in magnetic confinement fusion research amounts to more than a billion dollars per year. The effort is roughly equally distributed among the four large programs. Generally speaking, all of these programs are technically equal. Considering the long-term nature of fusion research, the wide geographical distribution of the work, the difficulty of the science, and the lack of military interest, there has been great interest in international cooperation to accelerate progress. The OECD nations have been working since 1983, under the auspices of the Economic Summit, to achieve more effective collaboration. Discussions on how to eliminate needless duplication revealed that all of the OECD fusion programs had adopted the same goal for the next step in fusion development. Separate bilateral discussions confirmed that the Soviet Union also shared the same goal. The goal, which all programs agreed was essential for future progress in fusion, was to complete the scientific base of the tokamak approach and to address the engineering issues of fusion energy. Achieving this goal requires the construction of at least one new facility that came to be known by the generic name of Engineering Test Reactor (ETR).

Figure I: Successful ETR development requires progress in other programs and experiments

Remarkably, there was also broad agreement on both the preparatory R&D and the timing of the ETR. Figure I shows the general outline of the program that was envisioned by the major fusion programs. The top line reflects the schedule of the pacing element, the ETR. Its basic function is to demonstrate the ignition and extended burn of Deuterium-Tritium (D-T) plasmas. However, the ETR is also required to validate engineering design concepts and qualify engineering components for a fusion reactor. It should, in addition, demonstrate the reliability of its engineering systems and the maintainability of a reactor. Finally, it must do the above in a manner that serves to enhance the potential for safe and environmentally acceptable operation of a power producing fusion reactor. These latter functions add considerably to the scope of the ETR, but all of the world's programs agree that it is necessary for the timely development of practical fusion power. Since it appears that the first practical fusion reactors will operate at the 500-1000 MWe level, an ETR, with all of the above characteristics, is essential in order to develop a complete technology base before the construction of the first reactor.

The data from existing experiments is adequate to begin the design of an ETR, but there are many development tasks that must be completed before such an ambitious device could be built. Figure I shows the general categories of this supporting development. Plasma technology consists of those technologies that are required to produce a fusion reaction. Most of these technologies are in use, in one form or another, in fusion research today. A great deal is known about these technologies, but each must be further developed to meet the requirements of an ETR. The Fusion Technology category consists of those technologies required to deal with the nuclear aspects of fusion power. During the scientific phase fusion experiments have used only small quantities of tritium in order to minimize the activation of the facilities. Some development of these technologies has been done using fission reactor experience and special test facilities, but much more remains to be done.

The final categories of supporting research concern fusion science. The set of large tokamak experiments--JET (EC), JT-60 (Japan), and TFTR (U.S.)--have already produced scientific results that suffice to start a realistic ETR design. They are all presently conducting specific experiments aimed at improving the scientific base, in order to allow improvements as the design proceeds. These experiments are supported, in turn, by a larger number of smaller devices. Together with the large new superconducting magnet tokamaks, T-15 (USSR), and Tore Supra (EC), these experimental facilities seem sufficient to support the ETR design in all areas of science, save one.

The one area of science in which existing experimental facilities are inadequate is understanding the physics of a plasma sustained by internally generated fusion energy--the physics of ignition by alpha particle heating. It would be possible to explore this physics as the first phase of an ETR. It is also possible to build a much smaller and less costly facility to provide earlier operating experience for the ETR by exploiting the high magnetic field tokamak approach.⁴

Detailed technical planning of how to accomplish the R&D outlined in Figure I has been carried out in each of the major fusion programs. Long-term development plans have been prepared by all of the world's fusion programs in varying degrees of detail. The most recent and complete is described in the 'Technical Program Analysis Report' prepared by the U.S. Department of Energy. This planning activity was unique in that it started from the existing world fusion effort and produced a functional plan for reaching the technical goals outlined in Figure I. The plan is both technically comprehensive and independent of national programs. It is an initial attempt at a world fusion development plan that could be carried out by the world fusion programs, in order to reach their common goal in the most efficient fashion. At the very least, this plan provides a convenient framework for coordinating the technical aspects of the many bilateral and multilateral agreements that have already been concluded. It serves as a scorecard of progress in fulfilling the program summarized in Figure I.

THE STATUS OF FUSION SCIENCE

Most of the effort in fusion research over the past 35 years has been spent in developing the science of plasma physics. That the effort has been remarkably successful as witnessed by the many points of agreement between theory and experiment in magnetic confinement fusion research. The agreement is by no means complete. A very important example is that the specific mechanism responsible for the turbulent energy and particle transport in tokamaks is not yet understood. Yet, even in this area, as the transport is measured with increasing precision in more realistic thermonuclear plasma experiments, a qualitative relationship to the predictions of theory is beginning to emerge. Experiments have borne out the qualitative theoretical prediction that ion acoustic wave turbulence and the associated ion heat transport should decrease as the plasma density gradient steepens. TFTR (U.S.) has observed the ion heat conductivity to decrease and the ion temperature to increase by a factor of ten under precisely these conditions. There is growing reason to believe that a fundamental understanding can be reached, even in this most difficult area.

Lack of fundamental understanding of tokamak energy transport means that the performance of future experiments can only be extrapolated from current results. The design of new experiments must compensate for the resulting uncertainty by including extra margin in their technological requirements. This is not a major problem if the cost of the extra margin is reasonable. The required margin depends on the size of the extrapolation from present experience. In the case of fusion, it should be recognized that magnetic confinement experiments are now working with realistic fusion plasmas. In magnetic confinement research, all of the individual plasma parameters required for an ignition experiment or an ETR have been achieved in separate experiments, and many have been achieved simultaneously. In terms of individual plasma parameters, the extrapolations are modest.

This can be seen in Figure II, which shows the ion temperature as a function of the product of density and confinement time achieved in recent (1988) magnetic and inertial confinement experiments. To a fusion scientist, the most striking evidence of progress in Figure II is that the results of magnetic confinement experiments and the ultimate goal of those experiments can now be shown on a linear plot. The magnetic confinement approach is within a factor of ten of the scientific goal of ignition. (Based on these results, the U.S. is considering a Compact Ignition Experiment (CIT)⁶, which should be able to explore the physics of ignition by the late 1990s.

Figure II: Magnetic confinement experiments are now producing plasmas with fusion-quality ion temperature and energy confinement. The three large tokamaks--JET (EC), JT-60 (Japan), and TFTR (U.S.)--have provided sufficient scientific information to design and ignited plasma experiment (CIT).

Figure II is useful in showing the progress toward fusion scientific goals. However, it does not fully reflect progress relative to the ultimate goal of practical fusion energy. The overall index of progress in fusion

research is the triple product of the ion temperature, the energy confinement time, and the density in a given plasma. This quantity is proportional to the ratio of the fusion energy released from a hot plasma to the energy used in heating the fuel initially. It is, therefore, a measure of how much useful energy can be released by a particular fusion approach. TFTR (U.S.) has produced the highest product in a magnetic confinement experiment with a 32 keV ion temperature plasma.

Ignition is the final stage for magnetic confinement. The physics that will allow the CIT to ignite is the same as that required for an ETR, or even a full scale fusion reactor. This is the reason that the CIT design and the ITER design can proceed in parallel. The two experiments share the same physics base.

THE STATUS OF FUSION TECHNOLOGY

Progress in fusion technology over the last three years has been significant, and a considerable number of mutually beneficial international collaborative efforts have been established, which are helping to complete the technology base for ITER. Advances have been made in establishing the technology base for the superconducting magnets, as well as the plasma fueling and heating systems needed both for today's experiments and ITER. New assessments of the environmental, safety, and economic aspects of fusion have clearly identified the R&D paths that lead to an optimum fusion reactor.

SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNETS FOR FUSION

The successful completion of the International Energy Agency (IEA) Large Coil Task marked the establishment of the technology base for fusion superconducting magnets. This was a ten-year long, \$120 million dollar, cooperative project of the EC, Switzerland, Japan and the United States. The results demonstrated the ability to construct superconducting magnets and operate them, singularly, and in a toroidal geometry at fields up to 9 Tesla.

The focus of magnet development has now shifted to high field and pulsed magnet R&D. Both Japan and the EC are preparing the necessary test facilities. The emphasis is on the development of internally cooled cabled superconductors for use in the pulsed high field solenoids, shaping coils, and toroidal field magnets of a fusion engineering test reactor. High field tests have been initiated on a 14 Tesla toroidal field coil module in the U.S. A pulsed module is also being designed and fabricated by the U.S. for testing in the Japanese Superconducting Engineering Test Facility. Other development efforts underway in the EC, Japan, the U.S., and the U.S.S.R. include the investigation of coil protection, stability, heat generation, cooling, low loss joints and alternate conductor designs.

PLASMA HEATING AND FUELING TECHNOLOGY

Energetic neutral particle beams and high frequency electromagnetic waves have been shown to be capable of heating plasmas to thermonuclear temperatures. Long pulsed (20-30 seconds) positive ion based 80, 120 and 140 keV neutral beam systems have been developed for current experiments. Long pulse sources manufactured by RCA were installed on TFTR and D-III in 1987, and have operated very reliably. The TFTR (US) and JET (EC) experiments have exceeded their design specifications by injecting 28 MW and 21 MW, respectively, of neutral power into the plasma. Negative ion neutral beam systems are being developed for use up to 1 MeV and beyond, since recent experiments have shown that they can be used for current drive as well as heating.

Other methods of heating plasma use electromagnetic waves with frequencies ranging from megahertz to over a hundred gigahertz. The JET (EC) experiment has used eighteen megawatts at 23-57 MHz (the Ion Cyclotron Resonance Heating [ICRH] frequency for the experiment) to heat the ions to 8 keV. Two high power antennas were fabricated and installed on TFTR (U.S.), and a similar one has been constructed by the United States for installation on the Tore Supra (EC) experiment. The Soviet Union has shown

that millimeter waves are extremely useful, not only for heating electrons, but also for controlling plasma instabilities. The U.S. has established the industrial capability to manufacture 200 kW steady state tubes at 120 GHz. High power 140 GHz gyrotrons have also been tested in the pulsed mode up to 800 kW in the first stage of a program to produce 1 MW 250 GHz steady state tubes.

Solid hydrogen pellet injectors for plasma fueling have also been fabricated by the U.S. and placed in operation on TFTR (U.S.) and JET (EC). In addition, an improved U.S. centrifugal injector, capable of providing pellets at a rate of 10/second for tens of seconds, has been provided to Tore Supra (EC) to support a cooperative program on the long pulse operation of that unique superconducting plasma experiment. The equally necessary inverse of plasma fueling is plasma exhaust. Experiments conducted on ASDEX (EC), D-III-D (U.S.), JET (EC) and JT-60 (Japan) have demonstrated the effectiveness of magnetic divertors. Research carried out under the IEA Textor Agreement has also demonstrated the capability of pumped limiters. U.S.-developed pumped limiters have been installed on TEXTOR (EC) and Tore Supra (EC) as part of a joint research program.

TRITIUM HANDLING

Experiments on tritium processing and handling are carried out by the United States and Japan at the TSTA facility. The facility is designed to test the technology required to control, separate, and purify deuterium and tritium from the plasma exhaust. TSTA contains a full tritium processing loop and has the capability of handling up to 130 grams of tritium. The full processing loop became operational with tritium in 1988. It has operated with up to 100 grams of tritium circulating in the system, thus far. Studies are presently underway for expanding the capability of TSTA to allow testing of the technology for processing tritium from different blanket concepts. The system is also being used to test a tritium pellet injector for plasma fueling and new materials that can be used to store tritium. In addition, two new Japanese-developed components, a palladium diffuser and a ceramic electrolysis cell, are being tested. Both of these components represent a significant improvement of the present fuel cleanup technology for fusion tritium handling systems.

FUSION MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT

The world fusion materials program is attempting to develop new or improved materials that will enhance the economic and environmental attractiveness of fusion. This requires the development of a fundamental understanding of the properties and performance characteristics of materials under projected fusion reactor operating conditions. This program has utilized fission reactors and charged particle accelerators to simulate fusion reactor conditions. The data obtained is being used to develop a predictive capability for the expected performance at extended lifetimes in a fusion reactor environment.

Material development is the longest term element of the world fusion program. Testing facilities are scarce and expensive to operate. As a result, progress in this area is heavily dependent on international collaboration. As the world fusion programs prepare for the construction of a fusion engineering test reactor, more attention is being given to materials questions, and collaboration is expanding. In 1983, the U.S. and Japan established a long-term agreement for collaborative materials irradiation work in the High Flux Isotope Reactor (HFIR) and the Fast Flux Test Facility (FFTF). Recently, the IEA Implementing Agreement on Fusion Materials has been expanded to include collaboration in theory (using super computer methodology), ceramics, tritium breeding solids, and the development of a common data base. Canada, Japan, and the United States have also implemented a new Annex to the IEA Fusion Materials Agreement. The Agreement provides for a jointly funded set of experiments on tritium breeding. The U.S. and the USSR have also expanded their bilateral activities on fusion materials research to reduced activation alloys in preparation for the engineering test reactor.

FUSION ECONOMICS, SAFETY, AND ENVIRONMENT

Progress in fusion technology has not been limited to the development of practical components of a fusion reactor. There has also been progress in the development of safe and environmentally acceptable technology. The U.S., in particular, has an environment and safety program responsible for assessing and evaluating the environmental and safety issues related to the operation of fusion reactors. The program is responsible for providing the information required to allow fusion reactors to meet all the requirements for public and operator safety. The analytical effort has concentrated on the development of codes and models, which can demonstrate the operational and safety aspects of fusion systems under different conditions. The experimental effort has concentrated on tritium handling, activation product behavior, and liquid lithium safety. For example, experiments have been done in the U.S. on the implantation and permeation of tritium in plasma facing materials to determine the tritium inventory and release mechanisms. We have also studied the release of fusion reactor activation products by heating potential fusion materials to high temperatures and measuring the mobility of volatilized elements. The results of these studies have been factored into fusion development programs around the world with very good effect.

Within the last three years the U.S. has completed a comprehensive study (ESECOM) that assessed the environmental, safety, and economic aspects of fusion. This study has synthesized the available knowledge from fusion science, technology and safety programs. Since the science and technology base for fusion is incomplete, the conclusions of the study are necessarily tentative. The real situation especially the economics, could turn out worse than envisioned in the study. However, by clearly identifying the sensitive areas, the authors have stimulated movement of the R&D program in the direction required for the more positive conclusions of the Report.

The Report concludes that fusion reactors have the potential to be economically competitive with advanced fission reactors. In addition, given the low radioactive inventories and passive barriers to the release of those inventories, they should provide a high degree of demonstrable public safety from the consequences of reactor accidents. Finally, fusion reactors should substantially ameliorate the radioactive waste problem by eliminating or greatly reducing high level wastes.

Along with prior fusion reactor studies, the ESECOM report has helped to direct fusion R&D efforts toward the science and technology developments that could optimize the usefulness of fusion reactors. For example, considerable progress has been made in developing low activation materials for fusion reactor application. These materials should greatly improve the safety of the reactor and eliminate the long-term waste disposal problem for fusion.

Results of irradiation testing and metallurgical research on reduced activation compositions of ferritic and austenitic steels have demonstrated the value of elemental tailoring in the development of reduced activation alloys. Special attention is now being applied to the evaluation of the potential of a family of Magnesium-stabilized austenitic stainless steels as a candidate for application in the ITER design. Irradiation studies also show that selected vanadium alloys look promising for the longer term fusion reactor application.

INTERNATIONAL FUSION REACTOR DESIGN

In the spring of 1987, the Director General of the International Atomic Energy Agency invited representatives of the EC, Japan, the U.S., and the USSR to meet in Vienna, to discuss enhanced international collaboration in fusion. The representatives at this meeting agreed that the most valuable enhancement of fusion collaboration would be the joint design of the next step experiment in magnetic fusion. They also agreed that an ETR was the correct next step in fusion R&D for all the world's programs. Technical working groups developed both specific Terms of Reference governing the proposed activities, and a set of technical objectives for the ETR. Based on the information generated by the working groups, the representatives recommended participation in a four-Party activity to the respective political authorities.

In the fall of 1987, the Director General issued an invitation to the four Parties, through diplomatic channels, to join the activity in accordance with the Terms of Reference, under the auspices of the IAEA. After reviewing the proposed activities and the Terms of Reference at high governmental levels (the European Community Council of Ministers, the Japanese Cabinet, the Office of the President of the United States, and the Council of Ministers of the Soviet Union), the Parties accepted the Director General's invitation.

The name for the joint ETR facility, the International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER), was chosen for two reasons. First, the words, themselves, are quite descriptive of the various ETRs that the Parties had separately envisioned as their next large step in testing the science and technology of power from thermonuclear fusion. Second, the acronym ITER (pronounced "eater") is, itself, meaningful. ITER is the Latin word for "the way". In entering this agreement, all participants expressed their hopes and expectations that the ITER Conceptual Design Activities will open the way to even more effective international cooperation in energy development for the common good of mankind. The Terms of Reference call for an integrated international activity, with the objective of providing a design and supporting R&D that would be available for all Parties to use, either in their own national program, or as part of a larger international collaborative program. The ITER Conceptual Design Activities will attempt:

- (a) to define a set of technical characteristics for ITER and, subsequently, to carry out the design work necessary to establish its conceptual design;
- (b) to define future research and development needs and to draw up cost, manpower, and schedule estimates for the realization of such a device;
- (c) to define the site requirements for ITER, and to perform a safety and environmental analysis; and
- (d) to carry out, in a coordinated manner, specific validating research and development work supportive of the design activities.

The Definition Phase of the ITER activity has been concluded successfully, and the Design Phase will be finished in December 1990. The purpose of the Definition Phase was to define a common design for an experimental thermonuclear reactor, which could test the basic physics and technologies essential to practical fusion reactors for all parties. This was accomplished in November 1988.

Although ITER will release a great deal of fusion energy, it is not meant to be a fusion power reactor. It is an experimental reactor, the operation of which is essential for learning how to build a practical fusion reactor. As such, ITER represents a stage in the development of fusion rather than a finished product. It also follows that the ITER design will reflect the considerable uncertainty that still remains in both the science and engineering of fusion. The Definition Phase was also intended to identify a single design point that would serve as the focus of further development during the subsequent Design Phase. The team succeeded in defining the R&D required, both to reduce the uncertainty in the current design and to improve the performance of ITER as the design evolves. The Parties have agreed to provide this R&D, either through the direct contribution to ITER or through other voluntary contributions.

During the Definition Phase, a set of ITER technical characteristics was developed and documented in a Definition Phase Report. This Report also contains the plan for ITER supportive R&D activities that will be performed by the Parties. The Definition Phase Report was produced by the ITER team participants from the EC, Japan, U.S., and the USSR, who gathered in Garching, West Germany, on May 2, 1988, to carry out the definition work. This core group was supported by their home teams and R&D activities. They also benefited greatly from the participation of hundreds of other scientists and engineers who participated in specialist workshops.

It was recognized by all parties to the ITER activity that reaching its objectives will require the dedicated effort of many of the very best fusion scientists and engineers, as well as the extensive technical support of the world's fusion programs. During the Definition Phase, the ITER activity has succeeded in attracting a high level of scientific and engineering talent, a level that is continuing through the Design Phase. With completion of the Design Phase scheduled for the end of 1990, the ITER participants are beginning to consider what should succeed this current activity.

CONCLUSION

Magnetic confinement research has demonstrated the ability to produce controlled thermonuclear fusion conditions in the laboratory. As a result, fusion research is turning from the question of scientific feasibility to the question of engineering feasibility. Another generation of experiments is required to complete the scientific base and to address the issues of fusion engineering. The science and technology developed over the last few years seem to be adequate to undertake this new stage of development. The scientific facts, as they are now understood, indicate that the facilities needed to address the issues of engineering feasibility will, themselves, generate 500-1000 MW of power in the case of magnetic fusion, or 500-1000 MJ per pulse in the case of inertial fusion. In addition, the problems to be solved are such that the preparation, the construction and the operation of these facilities could be shared by several nations. International collaboration offers one way to reduce the cost and spread the risk of such large facilities. Experience gained in the ITER activities leads me to believe that fusion can be developed surely and rapidly as a global project.

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